

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN UNIVERSITIES: FROM ADAPTIVE LEARNING TO INTELLIGENT ANALYSIS OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Annotation. In the context of active digital transformation of the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the introduction of innovative technologies, including artificial intelligence, in higher education processes. The purpose of this study is to analyze the potential for using artificial intelligence in universities of Uzbekistan - from adaptive learning and intelligent analysis of academic performance to automation of teaching. The article discusses key areas of using artificial intelligence: personalization of educational trajectories, implementation of virtual assistants, predictive analytics systems and adaptive platforms. The methodological basis of the study includes a review of domestic and foreign scientific publications, as well as an analysis of current initiatives within the framework of national digitalization programs, such as Digital Uzbekistan - 2030. The main advantages of using artificial intelligence are identified: improving the quality of education, individualizing approaches to students, reducing the administrative burden on teachers. At the same time, current problems are identified: lack of qualified personnel, weak IT infrastructure in some regions, issues of ethics and cybersecurity. Based on the analysis, practical recommendations are proposed for the phased integration of artificial intelligence into the educational system of Uzbekistan, taking into account the local context.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, higher education, digitalization, adaptive learning, performance analysis, digital university.

1.Introduction

The modern system of higher education in Uzbekistan is undergoing a stage of active digital transformation, caused by the need to meet international quality standards, as well as the growing expectations of students and society as a whole. A number of initiatives aimed at modernizing the educational sphere are being implemented at the state level. Among them, special attention is paid to the introduction of advanced digital technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, as one of the key tools for improving the efficiency of learning and managing the educational process.

Within the framework of the national program "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030", one of the priorities is the development of a digital educational environment, including the introduction of intelligent systems in the activities of universities [5]. Also, the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of Uzbekistan supports projects aimed at integrating adaptive learning platforms and analytical systems based on AI into the educational process [6].

Despite significant interest in the use of AI in education, issues of its practical use in universities in Uzbekistan remain insufficiently studied. To date, the implementation of AI solutions is limited mainly to experimental or pilot projects, while there is no systematic approach and general methodological recommendations. Meanwhile, global experience shows that artificial intelligence can significantly increase the level of personalization of education, automate routine processes, facilitate management decision-making, and even predict the academic success of students [1], [2].

Thus, the need to study the possibilities of using AI in the context of universities in Uzbekistan is determined by both global trends and national priorities in the field of education. This study is aimed at

systematizing existing approaches, identifying prospects and limitations, and formulating practical recommendations for integrating AI into the educational practice of universities in the republic.

2. Materials and methods.

This study is based on a qualitative analytical approach, including a review of scientific literature, a comparative analysis of international and domestic practices, and a study of national strategic documents related to the digitalization of higher education in Uzbekistan.

The following sources were used in the study:

- scientific publications and peer-reviewed articles on the topic of AI application in education (2020–2024);
- reports of international organizations (UNESCO, OECD, World Bank) on the digitalization of education;
- state and regulatory documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "Strategy for Digital Uzbekistan - 2030", materials of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, analytics of the Ministry of Digital Development RUz ;
- examples of the implementation of AI systems in universities of Uzbekistan (for example, in NUUz, TATU, USU, SVUTU, etc.).

To achieve the set goals, the following methods were used:

1. Analysis of scientific literature. The method of analysis of scientific literature is a systematic study of existing publications and studies related to the topic of artificial intelligence (AI) in higher education. Within the framework of this method, a review of both domestic and foreign sources was conducted, including:

- analytical reviews that examine trends in the development of AI in education;
- empirical studies that use data on the implementation of AI in educational institutions;
- methodological recommendations developed for the use of AI in educational practice.

The purpose of this method is to summarize existing knowledge on the topic, identify key areas and problems associated with the use of AI in universities, and understand which methods and approaches are already successfully used in other countries [4].

2. Study of the legal framework. The method of analyzing the legal framework involves studying documents regulating the use of technologies in the field of education. In this case, special attention was paid to state strategies and programs for the digitalization of education developed by the Ministry of Digital Technologies and the Ministry of Higher Education of Uzbekistan. This included:

- analysis of state programs and plans aimed at the development of digital technologies in education, such as the "Digital Strategy of Uzbekistan";
- study of regulations that govern the use of new technologies in the educational process, including legislation concerning intellectual property and data security.

This method made it possible to assess the extent to which the existing legal and regulatory framework supports the introduction of AI in educational institutions and what legal restrictions exist for this [5], [6].

3. Content analysis of practical cases. Content analysis of practical cases includes the study of real examples of AI application in the educational process of universities. Specific educational institutions in Uzbekistan were studied, such as the National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent University of Information Technologies, Tashkent University of Applied Sciences and Samarkand State University. The analysis of these cases allowed:

- to assess the success and problems of introducing AI systems into the educational process;
- to identify best practices and approaches used in different universities;
- understand how AI technologies can help improve the quality of education, such as through personalized learning paths, automated assessment, and other solutions.

This method contributed to a deep understanding of how AI technologies impact the educational process and what experience Uzbekistan has in this area.

4. Comparative analysis. The comparative analysis is a comparison of the current state of AI implementation in higher education institutions of Uzbekistan with similar practices in other countries. For this purpose, a detailed analysis of foreign experience was conducted, with a special emphasis on:

- advanced educational systems that actively use AI technologies (for example, in the USA, Great Britain, South Korea);
- innovative approaches successfully applied in other countries, such as the use of AI for performance analysis, adaptive learning, virtual assistants and chatbots;

– assessing how these practices can be adapted in Uzbekistan, taking into account local specificities.

A comparative analysis made it possible to identify key problems and potential for introducing international practices into Uzbek universities [1], [7].

5. Generalization and systematization of data . This method consisted of structuring all the data obtained, which made it possible to identify the main areas of application of AI in universities in Uzbekistan. During the systematization, the following were identified:

- key trends in the use of AI, such as the growing interest in adaptive learning and big data analysis;
- the main barriers to AI implementation, such as lack of qualified personnel and lack of funding;
- development prospects, including the possibilities of integrating AI into educational platforms and distance learning systems.

This method allowed us to create a clear picture of the current state and identify opportunities for improvement and further development of AI in higher education in Uzbekistan.

In addition, elements of an expert approach were used: when formulating conclusions, the opinions of representatives of the academic and IT environment, reflected in publications and open interviews, were taken into account.

This approach allowed us to obtain a comprehensive picture of the current level and potential of AI use in universities in Uzbekistan, as well as to identify the main barriers and growth points on the path to digital transformation of education in the republic.

3.Results.

Based on the analysis of current practices, literary sources and regulatory documents, several key areas of application of artificial intelligence in universities of Uzbekistan were identified. Each of them is already being implemented to varying degrees or is considered as promising for integration into the educational system.

1. Adaptive learning and personalization of educational trajectories .

One of the most promising areas is the implementation of adaptive learning platforms that use AI to adjust educational content to the level and learning style of a particular student.

Personalization of educational trajectories is the process of creating *individual learning paths* that best meet the needs and goals of each student. It is important to note that personalization is not limited to the choice of course or discipline, it includes:

Dynamic adaptation of content - depending on the results of midterm tests and assignments, the student can receive additional materials on weak topics.

Flexibility in choosing topics and disciplines - the student can choose which disciplines to study in what order, or arrange their study schedule at a time convenient for them.

Goals and career paths - educational pathways can be tailored to suit a student's professional interests, career goals, or preparation for specific exams.

Such systems analyze learner behavior, test results, and interaction with materials to offer an individual learning path [3].

In Uzbekistan, the implementation of adaptive educational platforms faces a number of challenges, such as a shortage of qualified IT specialists and high costs for developing relevant technologies. However, today, individual universities in the country are actively experimenting with elements of adaptive learning, introducing such technologies as part of pilot projects. For example, the Tashkent University of Information Technologies and the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences have successfully implemented programming courses with elements of adaptive learning, which allowed students to better master complex concepts through personalized recommendations and tests.

Another important step in the development of adaptive learning is the creation of a national strategy for the digitalization of education, which should include the development of platforms for online learning, the use of AI in managing the educational process, and the training of specialists in the field of digital technologies for the education sector.

In Uzbekistan, elements of adaptive learning are beginning to be implemented within LMS systems, in particular, based on Moodle and Canvas at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies, the National University of Uzbekistan, and the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences. However, the use of AI modules is still at an early stage, mainly in the form of experimental courses with elements of automated feedback and recommendations.

2. Intelligent data analysis and predictive analytics .

And artificial intelligence can analyze large amounts of data on students' academic performance, attendance, and activity in the digital environment. Based on this data, it is possible to identify students at risk, predict academic failure, and offer timely support measures [2].

Some universities in Uzbekistan, in particular Samarkand State University and Tashkent State University of Economics, have begun using BI systems with predictive analytics elements to monitor academic performance. The introduction of such systems is supported by initiatives of the Ministry of Higher Education within the framework of the program for digitalization of educational process management [5].

3. *Virtual assistants and intelligent chatbots.*

AI assistants can greatly facilitate communication between students and the university. They are used to automatically answer frequently asked questions, navigate the schedule, register for courses, and even provide study assistance.

In Uzbekistan, similar projects have been implemented on the basis of Telegram bots at the Fergana Polytechnic Institute and the Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering. These bots are connected to the university's internal databases and allow students to quickly receive the necessary information. However, this is limited to simple functions so far, and not all such solutions are based on full-fledged artificial intelligence .

4. *Automation of routine teacher tasks.*

And artificial intelligence is also used to automatically check tests, generate assignments, create individual assignments, and even evaluate written work. Such tools significantly save teachers' time and improve the objectivity of assessment.

A number of universities in Uzbekistan use plugins based on artificial intelligence to automatically check tests and essays on the Moodle platform . However, there is no centralized support for such initiatives at the ministry level.

5. *Ensuring inclusiveness and support for students.*

Ensuring inclusion and support for students is a key aspect of the modern educational process, especially in the context of digital transformation. Including students with different needs and creating equal opportunities for all participants in the educational process is an important task for universities, especially considering that AI technologies can significantly contribute to improving the quality of learning and increasing accessibility of education for everyone.

Inclusion in education is about creating equal opportunities for all students, regardless of their physical, cognitive or socioeconomic differences. It is important that education is accessible and effective for students with special needs and for those who may face various difficulties, such as students from low-income families, students with disabilities or international students.

AI not only promotes inclusion, but also plays a vital role in supporting students by providing better assistance and monitoring their progress. AI technologies can be applied in several key areas to improve student support:

Early identification of problems and assistance with learning. AI can analyze student behavior, successes, and difficulties to identify those who may be struggling academically. For example, *performance analytics systems* can analyze student behavior, such as late assignments or low grades, and offer additional resources or help from teachers.

Automate recommendations for support. AI systems can provide students with personalized recommendations on what courses, materials, or resources they should take to improve their academic performance. This can be especially useful for students who are struggling with learning, helping them navigate through large amounts of educational content more quickly and efficiently.

Chatbots and virtual assistants. AI-powered chatbots can be used to provide students with 24/7 support, such as answers to questions about their coursework, schedule, or technical issues. Virtual assistants can help students with time management, assignment planning, and reminders about due dates.

Psychological support and help in stressful situations . With the help of AI, it is possible to create systems to provide psychological support to students. For example, AI-based applications can analyze the emotional state of students, predict stressful situations and recommend calming methods or contact a school psychologist for additional help. This is especially important for students experiencing stress, depression or anxiety.

Examples of using such solutions in Uzbekistan are isolated, but pilot programs on digital inclusion are being implemented within the framework of international projects (for example, Erasmus + and TEMPUS). Such technologies, with the support of the state, could significantly expand access to education for all categories of citizens.

6. *Limitations and barriers to the implementation of AI in universities of Uzbekistan.*

Despite the potential, there are objective difficulties in Uzbekistan:

- low level of digital infrastructure in the regions;
- insufficient IT competence of teachers and administrators;
- lack of centralized standards for the use of AI in education;
- legal and ethical issues (e.g. processing of students' personal data).

However, with targeted government support and cooperation between universities and IT companies, these barriers can be overcome in the coming years.

4. Discussion .

The results of the analysis showed that the use of artificial intelligence technologies in universities of Uzbekistan is at an early but promising stage of development. There is a growing interest on the part of government agencies, universities and teachers in the integration of artificial intelligence into the educational process. At the same time, significant differences were identified between current practice and global trends in this area.

At the global level, in countries with highly developed educational IT infrastructure, artificial intelligence is already being actively used to create personalized learning paths, automatic assessment systems, predictive analytics, and digital tutors. Examples of such solutions include Squirrel AI systems in China, the ALEKS platform in the United States, and projects at MIT and Stanford universities aimed at introducing AI into campus life [1].

In comparison, the implementation of artificial intelligence in universities in Uzbekistan is fragmented . As a rule, these are local initiatives implemented by enthusiasts within individual departments or faculties. There is no unified state strategy for the integration of artificial intelligence into the higher education system, standards for assessing the effectiveness of such solutions, or specialized personnel.

However, Uzbekistan has serious prerequisites for the accelerated implementation of AI in education:

- Active implementation of the national program “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” provides for the development of digital universities and improving the digital literacy of teachers [5].
- A growing number of IT specialists and startups are ready to offer intelligent solutions to universities.
- Support for international projects (e.g. Erasmus +, KOICA, DAAD) that facilitate the transfer of experience and technology.

Particular attention should be paid to the ethical aspects of the implementation of artificial intelligence. It is necessary to take into account the rights of students to privacy, fair assessment and protection of personal data. Regulations are already being introduced in European countries that limit the use of AI in the educational environment without due transparency [4]. It is also important for Uzbekistan to develop similar mechanisms.

Based on the data obtained, five key areas of application of artificial intelligence in universities of Uzbekistan can be identified. Each of them has a different level of development and practical implementation. The table below provides a generalized comparison in these areas.

Tables №1. Generalized comparison of key areas of AI application

Direction of application of AI	Description	Implementation level (0-10)
Adaptive learning	Using intelligent platforms to personalize the learning process.	6
Predictive Analytics	Predicting academic performance and dropout risk using machine learning.	4
Digital assistants	Chatbots and voice assistants for student consultations.	5
Automatic knowledge assessment	Test and essay checking with AI elements.	5
AI in Learning Management	Recommender systems and automation of individual trajectory generation.	3

As can be seen from the table, the most developed direction is *adaptive learning*. This is explained by its high relevance, support at the level of educational policy and interest from students. There are already examples of the implementation of such systems in large universities of Uzbekistan, especially in technical and pedagogical universities.

Predictive analytics, *digital assistants* and *automated knowledge assessment* are at **an average level of development**. These technologies have begun to be implemented in pilot projects, but have not yet become widespread due to a lack of specialized specialists, localized solutions and regulatory frameworks.

The least developed area is *AI in learning management*. This is due to the fact that such systems require a comprehensive IT infrastructure, integration with student databases and high maturity of management processes. However, it is this area that has great strategic potential for building an intelligent educational ecosystem.

Thus, the results of the analysis show that Uzbekistan is at the stage **of transition from the experimental implementation of AI** to a systemic approach, which requires the consolidation of efforts of universities, the state and technology partners.

Thus, despite the current barriers, conditions are being created in Uzbekistan for the gradual and strategically verified introduction of artificial intelligence in universities. This will require efforts from the state, universities, developers and the scientific community, but can become the basis for a qualitative leap in the development of national education.

5. Conclusion.

The results of the study confirmed the high relevance of the use of artificial intelligence technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan. The analysis showed that, despite the limited large-scale implementation, AI is already used in a number of areas: adaptive learning, performance analysis, automation of teaching and virtual student support.

The use of AI opens up wide opportunities for:

- personalization of students' educational trajectories;
- increasing the objectivity and effectiveness of knowledge assessment;
- predicting the risks of dropping out and other academic problems;
- optimization of the administrative workload of teachers;
- expanding access to education for students with disabilities.

However, the systematic implementation of AI in universities in Uzbekistan requires a comprehensive approach. First of all, it is necessary:

1. *Develop a national strategy* for integrating AI into higher education, taking into account ethical, legal and infrastructural aspects.
2. *Enhance digital literacy of teachers*, including training in the basics of AI and digital pedagogy.
3. *Create centers of excellence* for EdTech and AI based at the country's leading universities.
4. *To stimulate cooperation between universities and IT companies and start-ups* specializing in educational technologies.
5. *Establish a legal framework* that ensures the protection of personal data and the ethical use of AI.

Thus, artificial intelligence can become not just an auxiliary tool, but a catalyst for qualitative changes in the system of higher education in Uzbekistan. With a strategic approach and coordination of efforts of all participants in the educational process, the republic is able to take a worthy place among countries that effectively use AI in education and management.

References

1. Holmes W., Bialik M., Fadel C. Artificial Intelligence in Education: Promises and Implications for Teaching and Learning. - M.: Center for Rethinking Education, 2021. - 122 p.
2. Ifenthaler D., Yau JY-K. Utilizing learning analytics to support study success in higher education: A systematic review. // *Educational Technology Research and Development*. — 2020. — T. 68. - S. 1961–1990.
3. Chen L., Chen P., Lin Z. Artificial intelligence in education: A review. // *IEEE Access*. — 2020. — T. 8. - S. 75264–75278.
4. UNESCO. Guidelines for the Ethical Use of Artificial Intelligence in Education. — Paris: UNESCO Publishing, 2022. — 54 p.
5. Ministry of Digital Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" [Electronic resource]. - Tashkent, 2023.

6. Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Report on the digital transformation of universities [Electronic resource]. - Tashkent, 2023.
7. UNESCO. Artificial Intelligence and Education: Guidance for Policy-makers. — Paris: UNESCO, 2021. — 144 p.
8. Clark R., Mayer R. E-learning and the Science of Instruction: Proven Guidelines for Consumers and Designers of Multimedia Learning. - 4th ed . — New Jersey: Wiley, 2016. — 528 p.
9. Saidalieva Sh.Sh., Nurmatov A.B. Innovative approaches to digitalization of education in universities of Uzbekistan // *Pedagogical education and science* . - 2022. - No. 4. - P. 115-119.
10. Karimov A.T. Prospects for the introduction of artificial intelligence in the educational process of higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan//*Bulletin of innovative education* . - 2023. - No.1 (25).- P. 34-40.
11. Sodikova Nigora , Muxtorova Zilola . Problems of digital transformation of education and their impact on scientific education // *Of softwareengineering and applied sciences* . Volume 1, Issue 2 [1] Published: 01/21/2025. 43-47 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14769625>
12. _Sodikova Nigora . Use of digital technologies in the course of practical training for economics majors in higher education // *International bulletin of engineering and technology* (Vol. 3, Issue 11, pp . 5–8). Zenodo . <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10081214>
13. _Sodikova Nigora , Aliyeva Nodira . The development of Uzbekistan's digital economy and its primary directions // *Eurasian magazine academic research* , 3(10), 245–250.
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